

Mishko Ralev, Viktorija Eremeeva Naumoska, Ana Krleska:
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Abstract

The motivation and satisfaction of employees, has been a challenge for businesses and academia alike to explore. One part of the academic world underlines monetary rewards as an extrinsic motivational tool, whilst others say that it has a limited effect on the employees' overall performance and that a well designed workspace environment shows much better results in relation to one's job satisfaction and performance (Ouedraogo & Leclerc, 2013). However, the research carried out in EU companies reveals that although the relationship between the workspace and job satisfaction has been investigated from the perspectives of sociology, psychology, management and medicine, there has been a lack of research from the standpoint of architecture and interior design (Danielsson & Bodin, 2008). Although there is a rising awareness of the importance of this issue among human resource departments in EU companies, knowledge and awareness in Macedonian companies remains unexamined. The aim of this study is to investigate the relationship between the physical workspace environment and the job satisfaction of employees in the banking industry in Macedonia. Using a specially designed survey based on existing research carried out in EU companies, the job satisfaction of employees was evaluated in the context of their workspace. This research also analyzed the architectural characteristics of office buildings, office layout and office décor. The findings show that there is a positive correlation between job satisfaction and the opportunity for the personalization of office space. Designated space for formal or informal meetings also positively influences job satisfaction. Negative correlations were evident between job satisfaction and elements determining a defocus from work. Tenure and satisfaction with office space were also negatively correlated with tenure at the same work station. The results were compared against findings from relevant EU research done in the field, and as a result recommendations have been made on how to increase job satisfaction among bank employees through workspace design.

Keywords: workspace environment, office space design, workplace satisfaction, job satisfaction.

Introduction

The configuration of the contemporary (modern) city silhouette is structured mostly by the modern office buildings which dominate the urban landscape, among which the banks, insurance companies and similar buildings of the finance industries dominate the skyline. They manifest economic strength and a belief in the future, representing themselves as an institutional symbol and urban icon. They very often embody the most developed building technologies in a specific architectural language, positioning them as the most progressive office buildings of the time (Danielsson, 2005). In addition, the inner working environments of these buildings are characterized by a rich and complex structure of spaces in order to fulfill the complex needs of the organizational diversity of a bank's workforce divided into numerous departments, creating a rich social life in each building, thereby enhancing and supporting encounters and interactions between all users of the space. As in many other industries, human resource management, especially employee satisfaction and motivation, is considered to lie at the heart of all development processes in the banking industry. Employee job satisfaction becomes even more important if we consider its influence on the quality and level of service delivered to customers. Researchers advocate that high quality customer service is delivered by employees who have experienced higher levels of job satisfaction (Kakkos et al., 2010). Unfortunately, the competitive scenario of today's banking business results in deteriorating social conditions in companies thereby undying low job satisfaction and employee turnover. These conditions were especially evident at the time of the European financial crisis, resulting in budget cutting, freezes in the hiring of staff, employee downsizing and a lack of development funds and opportunities (Shukla & Sinha, 2013). Therefore an understanding of the determinants of employee job satisfaction is vital against the restrictions that have been brought about by the adverse effects of the economic crises.

Apart from the political challenges, the last 25 years of independence of Macedonia, have also brought many changes to its banking sector. The Macedonian banking system currently consists of 18 private banks, 9 savings houses and the State owned Macedonian bank for development and promotion. More than 60% of total market activities are conducted by three banks. Another characteristic is that the local banks have recently been acquired by foreign investors, namely the Dutch-owned Demir-Halk Bank with over 60% of the shares of Export and Credit Bank AD Skopje and by

Steiermaerkische Bank und Sparkassen AG, from Austria with 100% of the shares in Investbank AD Skopje. As has been the case in many other countries in the world, the trends of globalization and liberalization have lead banks to create a more competitive approach in their everyday business activities. This included the introduction of new technology such as e-banking services, ATM machines and other technological changes that also resulted in a change in the patterns of work of the typical bank employee. In the light of the above, this chapter aims to investigate the relationship between employee job satisfaction in the banking industry and their workspace characteristics.

Literature Review

Job satisfaction is the most researched subject in the organizational behavior field of study. Increased academic attention paid to employee satisfaction results from the shift from manufacturing to service industries within developed countries in the last 20 years, thereby transforming the factory worker into a knowledge-based worker (Sousa-Poza & Sousa-Poza, 2000).

A review of the literature reveals a variety of definitions of job satisfaction and its determinants. According to Locke (1969) job satisfaction is defined as: "a pleasurable emotional state resulting from the appraisal of one's job as achieving or facilitating the achievement of one's job values" (p. 316). Robbins and Judge stated that job satisfaction is more an attitude than behavior and they define it as a "...positive feeling about one's job resulting from an evaluation of its characteristics" (Robbins & Judge, 2009, p. 65). The factors that determine job satisfaction include the perception of the job itself, relationships with colleagues and supervisors, feelings of job security, self-accomplishment and self-fulfillment, satisfaction with salary, and opportunities for promotion and advancement (Weis et al., 1967; Robbins & Judge, 2009). However in some cases a low level of job satisfaction can be attributed to a disconnection between what one expects and what one receives (Robinson and Rousseau, 1994). More specific factors that depend on personal traits are opportunities to learn and enhance work skills, being recognized for one's work and an opportunity to advance within the organization while achieving greater autonomy (Diala & Nemani, 2011, p. 829) Also they presumed that job satisfaction is much influenced by:

- Personality traits which workers bring to work
- Extrinsic values that come from outside individual, physical and financial resources, and other conditions that affect the environment in which people work
- Intrinsic values are structured from elements such as job responsibility, a feeling of achievement, growth potential, self-esteem, challenging work, and a sense of belonging
- Working conditions represent the quality of the work environment where employees spend most of their time outside the home. This includes other work situations that are used to determine job satisfaction, such as interactions between management and employees, the provision and availability of the necessary working tools and other resources for performing work tasks, and sick leave (Diala & Nemani, 2011).

The determinants have been analyzed in terms of the demographic characteristics of employees. For example, many studies carried out across different industries have found that female workers tend to experience higher levels of job satisfaction by comparison with male workers (Oshagbemi, 2000; Bender, Donohue & Heywood, 2005). By contrast, another stream of academic research finds that men are more satisfied than women with their jobs (Crossman & Abou Zaki, 2003; Okpara, 2006). However this difference in gender segregation regarding job satisfaction could be the result of different factors that range from cultural conditions (gender restricted access to labor market) to workplace opportunities (such as job flexibility, or extended maternity leave) (Bender et al., 2005). Research has also found that job satisfaction increases with age and tenure in the organization (Lee & Wilbur, 1985; Bedeian, Ferris & Kacmar, 1992). Older employees and those who have spent more time in the organization, tend to experience higher levels of job satisfaction by comparison with younger employees and employees who were new to the organization. Regarding the relationships between job satisfaction and company size, research suggests that job satisfaction is lower among employees working in larger companies. This can be attributed to weaker employee-manager relationships, as well as to inflexibility in the working environment that characterizes larger workspaces (Gazioglu & Tansel, 2002). Bluysen, Aries, and Dommelen (2011) indicate that most European or even world-wide organizations, confirm that work as well as living space, could have a major influence on people's well-being. Building conditions are refer to comfortable temperatures, air quality, natural and artificial lighting, moisture,

mould and noise. The conditions of interior design refer to both primary interior elements: such as the structure of architectural elements, the shape of the office plan, and office layout; as well as secondary interior elements, such as: the design of furniture systems, the color of interior space and its elements. Also elements of architectural décor play a great role in the design of the interior as a whole.

Job Satisfaction and Workspace Design

People spend many of their working hours at their workstations, which raises the possibility that the physical conditions that they are exposed to will influence their overall level of job satisfaction. A review of the literature reveals that people who live in industrialized countries spend approximately 90% of their time doing indoor work. The physical work environment, such as office space and workstation design, is provided by management for the employee, and can therefore be considered as an expression of management's attitudes towards the employee. Newsham et al. (2009) consider this has a two way relationship – the satisfaction of the employee with his/her workstation and office design could contribute to higher satisfaction with the job as with other aspects of the employment relationship.

Although job satisfaction has long been the focus of attentions for researchers in organizational science, the relationship between workspace design and job satisfaction is less prevalent in the literature. One of the earliest studies investigating this relationship was carried out in the field of environmental psychology by Sundstrom (1986) and examined the effect of workspace design on individuals, with a special focus on offices. Special attention has been given to the outcomes such as job satisfaction, job performance and the assessment of symptoms of sick building syndrome –SBS (such as headaches, fatigue, a stuffy nose, and weakened eyesight) (Brasche, Bullinger, Morfeld, Gebhardt, & Bischof, 2001; Chao, Schwartz, Milton, & Burge, 2003). Apart from environmental psychology, there are three other fields of research dealing with working environments and their impact on workers. These are: organizational-oriented research; occupational health and architecture. Although the last of these fields has been studied less, all other fields recognize and understand the important role of architecture in organizations and its impact on workers.

Besides its impact on job satisfaction the nature of the work is an important factor that influences office design, so that the assumption is: a better workplace environment produces better job results and increased productivity (Hameed & Amjad, 2009). Wineman and Adhya (2007) examined the relationship between psycho-social measures and a set of objective measures of the spatial layout of the office. Their questionnaire survey and correlation analyses on job satisfaction scale and various psycho-social scales show that high levels of job satisfaction are associated with positive perceptions of other aspects of the workplace such as privacy, interaction support, a sense of community and autonomy (p. 7). In line with these findings, other researchers have also found that the physical elements of the workplace contribute to a reported level of job satisfaction. In the example low indoor air quality and a low room temperature is found to contribute to an increased prevalence of self-reported SBS symptoms and absenteeism (Aaras, Horgen, Bjorset, Ro & Walsoe, 2001; Brasche, Bullinger, Morfeld, Gebhardt & Bischof, 2001; Stenberg, Eriksson, Hoog, Sundell & Wall, 1994).

Methodology

The main objective of the study was to analyze the determinants of job satisfaction among bank employees in three major banks in the Republic of Macedonia with regards to the architectural characteristics of their work-place environments. The questionnaire used was self-administered and was completed by 179 employees in three major Macedonian banks. All questionnaires were anonymous and the banks were clearly informed that the information would be used for scientific purposes only. The whole survey was administered over a period of three months.

Questionnaire

The questionnaire used for the survey was a quantitative questionnaire, which was built upon questions used in other relevant academic surveys that analyzed job satisfaction and the spatial characteristics of workspace. The questionnaire consisted of two main sections. The first section consisted of questions that gathered socio-demographic information from the survey participants and the nature of their job (age, gender, *tenure*-time spent working at the current work station, and *supervision*-does employee supervise others?). The second part of the questionnaire contained questions related to

the overall experience of job satisfaction felt by employees, and the characteristics of their workstation which was analyzed through four variables. The first variable *defocus* – consisted of seven items that measured exposure to noise and visual distraction that defocused the employee from his/her work; the second variable *temperature* – consisted of two items to assess the perception of temperature levels in the office; the third variable *meetings* – consisted of three items and assessed the opportunity to organize formal and informal meetings in the building, as well as the opportunity to meet other colleagues while moving through the building; the final variable *personalization* – consisted of one item and evaluated the opportunity for the employee to personalize his/her own working station.

Analysis of Data

Several tests have been utilized for the analysis of the gathered data. First t test analyses were used to estimate differences in the level of job satisfaction with regards to gender and the opportunity for office personalization. ANOVA was used to test for differences in the level of reported job satisfaction among bank employees with regard to the time they spent working at the same work station. Secondly, the Pearson correlation coefficient was calculated for overall job satisfaction and the four variables representing the characteristics of the workstation. Finally, a multiple regression analysis was conducted using six predictors for job satisfaction (the four previously outlined variables together with gender and tenure).

Results and Discussion

The survey was administered among 179 bank employees in the Republic of Macedonia. The majority of respondents were female (61%). Only 11.7% of employees worked in an individual office, followed by 31.3% of employees who worked in shared offices. The majority of respondents in the survey were working in ocean style offices (57%).

The results from the independent sample t-tests shown in Table 1, indicate that there is not a significant difference in the level of job satisfaction between male and female bank workers in Macedonia ($p > 0.05$). The analysis also shows that the mean level of reported job satisfaction among women is 3.79, similar to that reported by male workers (3.69). These findings differ with the research literature which found significant differences in levels of job

satisfaction experienced by men and women (Forgione & Peters, 1982; Oshagbemi, 2000; Bender et al., 2005; Sharpio & Stern, 1975; Crossman & Abou Zaki, 2003; Okpara 2006)

Table 1 – Level of job satisfaction among males and females (results from independent samples t-test)

		Independent Samples Test									
		Levene's Test for Equality of Variances		t-test for Equality of Means						95% Confidence Interval of the Difference	
		F	Sig.	t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	Std. Error Difference	Lower	Upper	
JS	Equal variances assumed	1,623	,204	,680	174	,498	,109	,160	-,207	,425	
	Equal variances not assumed			,658	127,101	,512	,109	,166	-,219	,437	

The research also asked respondents whether they were provided with an opportunity to participate in office space planning and organization. The results from the t-tests suggests that there is a significant level of difference in the level of reported job satisfaction between employees who were provided with the opportunity to participate and those who were not asked for their opinion (Table 2).

Table 2 – Level of job satisfaction with regards to opportunity for office personalization (results from independent samples t-test)

		Independent Samples Test									
		Levene's Test for Equality of Variances		t-test for Equality of Means						95% Confidence Interval of the Difference	
		F	Sig.	t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	Std. Error Difference	Lower	Upper	
JS	Equal variances assumed	9,781	,002	-1,489	89	,140	-,337	,226	-,786	,113	
	Equal variances not assumed			-1,391	58,679	,170	-,337	,242	-,822	,148	

The research results using ANOVA showed that there is a significant difference in the level of reported job satisfaction among bank employees and the time they spend working at the same work station ($p < 0.05$). From the total number of employees who worked between one and five years ($N=104$) at their current work station, 65,4 % experienced a positive level of reported job satisfaction. From the group of employees who worked between six and ten years at the same workstation ($N=43$), 65% experienced a positive level of

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job satisfaction, while 16% had reported a negative level of job satisfaction (Table 3). These findings do not completely agree with the analyzed literature. These survey results demonstrate that younger employees have very high levels of job satisfaction. These can be attributed to their enthusiasm or the opportunity of participating in workplace design (Lee & Wilbur, 1985; Bedeian et al., 1992).

Table 3 – Cross tabulation of job satisfaction and time spent working at the current workstation

Cross tabulation	Job satisfaction					Total
	Very Low	Low	Neutral	High	Very High	
Less than 1 year	0	0	3	9	8	20
1-5 years	4	8	24	46	22	104
6-10 years	3	4	8	18	10	43
11-15 years	0	0	4	3	0	7
16-20 years	1	0	0	0	0	1
More than 20 years	0	0	1	0	0	1
Total	8	12	40	76	40	176

The results reported in Table 4, represent the significance of correlation among the variables, by summarizing the values of the Pearson Correlation coefficient. The results from the analysis indicate that at a 5% significance level, job satisfaction is positively correlated with the variable communication which encompasses the spatial opportunities provided by the bank facility to organize formal and informal meetings and meet with colleagues. In addition, job satisfaction is negatively correlated with the variable defocused (which encompasses the noise and visual distractions experienced by the employees while working at their workstation). At a 1% level of significance, job satisfaction is positively correlated with the variable personalization (which encompasses the opportunity for the employee to decorate his/her workstation).

Table 4 – Correlation matrix of job satisfaction and working conditions

		Correlations				
		JS	Defocused	Communi- cation	Personali- zation	Temperature
JS	Pearson	1	-,263*	,302**	,18 *	-,104
	Sig. (2-tailed)		,00	,000	,01	,171
	N	17	17	17	176	176
Defocused	Pearson	-, **	1	,001	-,052	,266**
	Sig. (2-tailed)	,000		,989	,49	,000
	N	17	17	17	179	179
Communication	Pearson	,302**	,00	1	,30 **	-,016
	Sig. (2-tailed)	,000	,98		,00	,833
	N	17	17	17	179	179
Personalization	Pearson	,181*	-,052	,303**	1	-,124
	Sig. (2-tailed)	,017	,49	,000		,098
	N	17	17	17	179	179
Temperature	Pearson	-,	,26 *	-,016	-,124	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	,171	,00	,833	,09	
	N	17	17	17	179	179

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

* . Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

The results of the regression analysis for job satisfaction are presented in Table 5. The multiple regression model with all six predictors produced $R^2 = .178$, $F(6, 178) = 6,103$, $p < .001$. As can be seen in Table 1, the defocused and communication variables had significant regression weights. The multiple regression results showed that the coefficient *defocused* had a significant negative weight (CI 95%; -0.408 - -0.094) which is in line with its sign from its correlation with job satisfaction. Its value is 0.252 indicating that it can change the reported level of job satisfaction by approximately 25.2%, after controlling for other variables in the model. On the other hand, the coefficient communication is significant at 5% level (CI 95%; 0.125-0.475) and it contributes 29.9% to the job satisfaction of bank employees, after controlling for other variables in the model. The Personalization, Temperature, Redesign and Tenure variables, were not statistically significant and did not contribute to the multiple regression model ($p > 0.05$).

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Table 5 – Results of multi-regression analysis

Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	,422 ^a	,178	,149	,953

a. Predictors: (Constant), Tenure, Personalization, Redesign, Defocused, Temperature, Communication

ANOVA^b

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	33,288	6	5,548	6,103	,000 ^a
	Residual	153,621	169	,909		
	Total	186,909	175			

a. Predictors: (Constant), Tenure, Personalization, Redesign, Defocused, Temperature, Communication

b. Dependent Variable: JS

Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	3,600	,542		6,642	,000
	Defocused	-,252	,080	-,232	-3,160	,002
	Communication	,299	,089	,251	3,344	,001
	Personalization	,072	,067	,079	1,071	,286
	Temperature	-,021	,081	-,019	-,263	,793
	Redesign	-,013	,147	-,006	-,091	,928
	Tenure	-,158	,097	-,119	-1,632	,105

a. Dependent Variable: JS

Conclusions and Recommendations

The aim of this study was to analyze how workspace design determines the level of job satisfaction among 179 employees in the Macedonian banking industry. The research found that there is not a significant difference in the level of job satisfaction between male and female bank workers in Macedonia, while a significant level of difference was found in the level of reported job satisfaction between employees who were provided with the opportunity to participate in their workspace design and those who

were not asked for their opinion. In addition the study found a significant difference in the level of reported job satisfaction among bank employees and the time they spent working at the same work station. Employees who had been in the company between one and five years demonstrated the highest level of job satisfaction. The analysis of workspace determinates of job satisfaction, suggested that factors that decreased the attention focus of employees (such as noise and visual disturbances) decreased the level of job satisfaction; while workspace opportunities for formal and informal meetings increased the level of job satisfaction reported by bank employees. These findings were in line with other studies carried out across different industries in Europe. This research is the first of its kind to be carried out in the Republic of Macedonia, and future research attempts should provide information that would contribute to a better understanding of the determinants of any workspace that create the highest level of job satisfaction.

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